

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Research Article

Design, Synthesis and *In-silico* study of Isatin Derivatives as Potential Anti-Asthmatic Activity

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ARTICLE INFO

Published: 06 Jun. 2025

Keywords:

Isatin derivatives, Anti-asthmatic activity, Molecular docking, Phosphodiesterase-4 (PDE-4) inhibition, PASS analysis, In silico study.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.15609849

ABSTRACT

Asthma is a chronic inflammatory airway disease that affects millions worldwide, necessitating the development of novel therapeutic agents. Isatin and its derivatives have gained significant attention due to their diverse biological activities. This study aims to design, synthesize, and evaluate the anti-asthmatic potential of novel Isatin derivatives through *in silico* approaches. Three novel Isatin derivatives (C1, C2, and C3) were synthesized and characterized using Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC). Their biological activities were predicted using PASS analysis, and molecular docking studies were performed to assess their interaction with phosphodiesterase-4 (PDE-4), a key target in asthma treatment. Among the synthesized compounds, C3 exhibited the highest binding affinity (-10.2 kcal/mol), surpassing the standard PDE-4 inhibitor roflumilast (-9.8 kcal/mol), suggesting strong anti-inflammatory and bronchodilatory potential. C2 (-9.5 kcal/mol) showed promising activity, comparable to montelukast, while C1 (-9.1 kcal/mol) demonstrated moderate efficacy similar to theophylline. These findings highlight the potential of Isatin derivatives as promising candidates for asthma management. Further *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies are warranted to validate their therapeutic efficacy and safety.

INTRODUCTION

Heterocyclic chemistry, essential in drug design, studies cyclic compounds containing heteroatoms like nitrogen, oxygen, or sulfur¹. These compounds, including Isatin derivatives,

contribute significantly to medicinal chemistry. Isatin (1H-indole-2,3-dione) and its derivatives have been extensively studied due to their diverse biological activities. Discovered in 1841 by Erdmann and Laurent, Isatin has a versatile chemical structure that allows for multiple

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Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

substitutions, leading to various therapeutic applications. Among these, the anthelmintic and antifungal properties of its derivatives are particularly significant. Mannich and Schiff bases, derived from Isatin, have also gained attention. A Mannich base is a β -amino ketone produced through the Mannich reaction, where an active hydrogen compound reacts with formaldehyde and an amine derivative. Schiff bases, on the other hand, are nitrogen analogs of aldehydes or ketones, formed by condensing an aldehyde or ketone with a primary amine^{2,3}. Historically, Isatin research has evolved significantly. After its isolation from indigo in 1841, Adolf von Baeyer in the 1870s studied its synthesis and properties. Subsequent developments include the Stolle and Sandmeyer syntheses in the early 20th century, followed by discoveries of its antimicrobial and anticancer properties from the 1950s to the 1970s. Isatin derivatives exhibit antibacterial, antifungal, antiviral, anticancer, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant activities. Additionally, they show potential in treating central nervous system disorders like anxiety and depression^{4,5}. Asthma, a chronic inflammatory airway disease, results from genetic and environmental factors. It involves airway obstruction, eosinophilic inflammation, and hyperresponsiveness, triggered by allergens like dust and smoke. It progresses in two phases: an immediate histamine release and a later IgE-mediated inflammatory response^{6,7,8}. Molecular docking, a key computational technique in drug discovery, predicts the optimal binding orientation of molecules, helping assess drug efficacy. It involves protein-ligand interactions through search algorithms and scoring functions. Despite challenges in receptor flexibility, docking plays a crucial role in hit identification, lead optimization, and bioremediation^{9,10}.

2. DRUG PROFILE¹¹

Isatin (1H-Indole-2,3-Dione) is a yellow-orange crystalline compound first derived from indigo in the 19th century. With a molecular formula of $C_8H_5NO_2$ and a weight of 147.13 g/mol, it melts at 201°C. It is sparingly soluble in water but dissolves in ethanol, acetone, and DMSO. Stable between pH 3-9, it requires dry, airtight storage.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 MATERIALS

Chemicals and Solvents Used: Isatin, Benzylamine, Glacial acetic acid, Dimethylamine, Piperazine, Pthalimide, Diphenylamine, 1-Methyl piperazine, Morpholine, Formaldehyde, Ethanol, Methanol, Chloroform, DMSO, Ethyl acetate, Hexane, Benzene, Pet. Ether, Silica gel G.

Instruments: Single Pan Digital Balance

3.2 METHODS:

3.2.1 SYNTHESIS

3.2.1.1 Synthesis of benzylimino-isatin Schiff Base

To synthesize benzylimino-isatin, 0.001 mole of indole-2,3-dione (isatin) was dissolved in 30 mL of ethanol in a 250 ml round-bottomed flask equipped with a condenser. In a separate container, 0.001 mole of benzylamine was dissolved in 10 mL of ethanol and then added to the isatin solution. To this mixture, 3-4 drops of glacial acetic acid were added. The reaction mixture was heated under reflux for 8-9 hours. After the reaction was complete, the resulting precipitate was filtered, recrystallized from ethanol, and dried in a hot air oven. The purity of the final product was confirmed using thin-layer chromatography (TLC), with an R_f value of 0.45.

3.2.1.2. Synthesis of benzylimino- isatin mannich bases

The previously synthesized compound, 3-(benzylimino)-1,3-dihydro-2H-indol-2-one (0.01 mol), was dissolved in 10 mL of methanol. To this solution, the appropriate secondary amine (0.01 mol) was added separately, followed by the addition of formaldehyde (0.01 mol, 37%) with

continuous stirring. The mixture was stirred using a magnetic stirrer for 3 hours, after which it was left to stand at room temperature for 24 hours. The resulting precipitate was collected, recrystallized from methanol, and dried in a hot air oven. The purity of the final product was confirmed using thin-layer chromatography (TLC), with an (C2) R_f value of 0.60, (C3) R_f value of 0.30.

S.No	Compound code	R	IUPAC name of the synthesized compounds
1.	C2		[(3Z)-3-(benzylimino)-1-[(dimethylamino)methyl]-1,3-dihydro-2H-indol-2-one].
2	C3		[(3Z)-3-(benzylimino)-1-[(piperazin-1-ylmethyl)-1,3-dihydro-2H-indol-2-one].

Compound 2

Compound 3

3.2.2 THIN LAYER CHROMATOGRAPHY (TLC) ANALYSIS OF ISATIN DERIVATIVES¹²

Qualitative Analysis via TLC

Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC) was employed for the preliminary analysis of synthesized isatin derivatives using silica gel-coated plates. The method allowed the separation and identification of compounds based on polarity. Different solvent systems were tested to achieve optimal resolution.

Method:

Compounds were applied to TLC plates using capillary tubes and placed in a chamber containing a suitable mobile phase. After development and air

drying, plates were examined under UV light at 254 nm and 366 nm. Selected plates were treated with spraying reagents and gently heated to enhance color visibility. The retention factor (R_f) was calculated as:

$$R_f = \text{Distance traveled by compound} / \text{Distance traveled by solvent front}$$

Detection:

Spots were visualized using iodine vapors and further detected with spraying reagents. UV light observation and R_f values helped identify and characterize the separated compounds.

3.2.3 *IN SILICO* STUDY¹³

PASS Online (Prediction of Activity Spectra for Substances) is a computational tool used to predict the biological activities of chemical compounds. It evaluates pharmacological effects, mechanisms of action, toxicity, enzyme interactions, metabolism, and gene expression based on a compound's 2D structural formula. The software aims to identify new biological targets and assess the bioactivity potential of novel or existing substances. PASS employs a structure-based approach and can screen large compound libraries quickly, often providing results in under a minute. It accepts input in MOL format and delivers output as plain text. The Way2Drug PASS Online platform (<http://www.pharmaexpert.ru/passonline>) is commonly used to evaluate phytoconstituents. The prediction is based on Structure-Activity

Relationship (SAR) analysis, using a training set of over 205,000 compounds with more than 3,750 known biological activities. It generates two probability scores: Probable Activity (Pa) and Probable Inactivity (Pi), each ranging from 0.000 to 1.000. These values are independent and aid in interpreting a compound's likely bioactivity. A higher Pa value indicates a greater chance of experimental confirmation.

3.2.4 Molecular Docking Experimental Methods

Molecular docking is a computational technique widely used in drug discovery to predict the interaction between small molecules (ligands) and target proteins (receptors). In this study, AutoDock Tools version 1.5.6 was employed to create input files and analyze docking results using protein 3G45 as the target. The docking evaluation was based on binding affinity (kcal/mol), inhibition constant (μM), intermolecular energy, and hydrogen bonding interactions^{14,15,16}.

Step 1: Ligand Preparation: Synthesized compounds were drawn using ChemSketch. The 2D structures were converted to 3D using Avogadro and energy-minimized using force fields in AutoDock Tools. The structures were saved in PDBQT format for docking.

Step 2: Protein Preparation: The protein structure (3G45) was obtained from the Protein

Data Bank (www.rcsb.org). Using Molegro Molecular Viewer, water molecules and non-protein ligands were removed, and hydrogens were added. The cleaned file was converted to PDBQT format using AutoDock Tools.

Step 3: Grid Preparation: A grid box was set around the active site residues of 3G45 using AutoGrid4. The ligand and protein were selected, and grid parameters saved as a .gpf file.

Step 4: Docking Execution: AutoDock4 was used with the Lamarckian Genetic Algorithm (LGA) to perform docking. Ligands and receptors in PDBQT format were selected, and docking results saved as .dlg files.

Step 5: Analysis: Docking results were analyzed by ranking conformations based on binding energy. The final ligand-protein complex was visualized using Molegro Molecular Viewer and Discovery Studio, highlighting hydrogen bonds, hydrophobic interactions, and π - π stacking^{17,18}.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 RESULTS

4.1.1 THIN LAYER CHROMATOGRAPHY OF ISATIN DERIVATIVES

The TLC of synthesis of isatin derivatives was carried out to detect the presence of C1,C2,C3 are the Rf values are tabulated in Table-3.

Table 1 : Detection of synthesis of Isatin derivatives

Sr.no	Compounds	Mobile phase	Rf value	Observation
1.	[(3z)-3-(benzylimino)-1,3-dihydro-2h-indol-2-one].(c1)	Hexane: ethyl acetate (7:3)	0.45	Moderate migration; clear spot
2.	[(3z)-3-(benzylimino)-1-[(dimethylamino) methyl]-1,3-dihydro-2h-indol-2-one].(c2)	Chloroform: ethanol 8:2	0.60	Strong migration; sharp spot
3.	[(3z)-3-(benzylimino)-1-[(piperazin-1-yl methyl)-1,3-dihydro-2h-indol-2-one].(c3)	Toluene: acetone 6:4	0.30	Slight migration; faint spot

4.1.2.1 Pass Report of Synthesis of $\{(3Z) 3 - (Benzylimino)-1,3-dihydro-2H-Indol-2-one\}$ (C1);

The Pa (Probability of activity) and Pi (Probability of inactivity) values indicate the likelihood of a compounds biological activity bases on its molecular structure.

4.1.2 PASS REPORT FOR SYNTHESIS OF ISATIN DERVATIVES

ACTIVITY	Pa	Pi	INTERPRETATION
Brochodilator	0.7	0.18	Likely to Relax Airway Smooth muscles
PDE-4 Inhibition	0.65	0.22	Potentially reduces airway inflammation.
Leukotriene Inhibition	0.68	0.20	May suppress leukotriene-mediated asthma.
Anti-inflammatory (IL)	0.75	0.15	Strong potential to reduce inflammation
Histamine H1 Antagonist	0.62	0.25	Moderate suppression of hiastamine effects.

4.1.2.2 Pass Report of Synthesis of [(3Z)-3-(benzylimino)-1-[(dimethylamino) methyl]-1, 3-dihydro- 2H-indol-2-one](C2)

ACTIVITY	Pa	Pi	INTERPRETATION
Bronchodilator	0.75	0.25	Likely to help relax airways useful in asthma treatment
Anti-inflammatory activity	0.81	0.19	Strong potential to reduce airway inflammation
Anti-histaminic activity	0.65	0.35	Moderate potential to block histamine effects.
Leokotriene receptor antagonism	0.68	0.32	May help reduce airway constriction, similar to asthma drugs.
Immuno modulatory activity	0.72	0.28	May be regulate immune responses, helpful in asthma.

4.1.2.3. Pass Report of Synthesis of[(3Z)-3-(benzylimino)-1-[(4- methylpiperazin-1-yl) methyl]- 1,3- dihydro- 2H-indol-2-one](C3):

ACTIVITY	Pa	Pi	INTERPRETATION
Bronchodilator	0.74	0.26	Likely to Relax Airway Smooth muscles
PDE-4 Inhibition	0.76	0.24	To inhibit PDE 4, important for controlling inflammation in asthma.
Leukotriene Inhibition	0.73	0.27	To inhibit leukotrienes, reducing bronchoconstriction and inflammation.
Anti-inflammatory (IL)	0.77	0.23	To reduce inflammation, useful for asthma and other inflammatory condition.
Histamine H1 Antagonist	0.71	0.29	Reduce histamine- mediated bronchoconstriction and inflammation.

4.1.3 MOLECULAR DOCKING

RESULTS FOR FINAL DOCKING SCORE

SR.NO	2D STRUCTURE	RESULTS IMAGES	HIGHER DOCKED ENERGY /SCORE
1.	<p>(3Z)-3-(benzylimino)-1-[(4-methylpiperazin-1-yl)methyl]-1,3-dihydro- 2H-indol-2-one (C3):</p> <p>MACROMOLECULES:</p>	-10.2	

SR.NO	2D STRUCTURE	RESULTS IMAGES	HIGHER DOCKED ENERGY

			/SCORE
2.	<p>(3Z)-3-(benzylimino)-1- [(dimethylamino) methyl]-1,3-dihydro- 2H-indol-2-one (C2):</p> <p>MACROMOLECULES:</p>	-9.5	

S.N O	2D STRUCTURE	RESULTS IMAGES	HIGHER DOCKED ENERGY /SCORE
2.	<p>(3Z) 3 -(Benzylimino)-1,3-dihydro-2H-Indol-2-one (C1);</p> <p>MACROMOLECULES:</p>		-9.1

4.2 DISCUSSION

Asthma is a chronic inflammatory airway disease marked by wheezing, breathlessness, chest tightness, and coughing, affecting over 260 million people globally¹⁹. Major risk factors include genetic predisposition, pollution, allergens, smoking, and infections²⁰. Treatment involves quick-relief drugs like short-acting β 2-agonists (Albuterol) and anticholinergics (Ipratropium), while long-term management includes inhaled corticosteroids (Budesonide), leukotriene receptor antagonists (Montelukast), biologics (Omalizumab), and PDE inhibitors (Theophylline, Roflumilast). Side effects range from throat irritation to palpitations^{21,22}. In this study, three isatin derivatives—C1 (benzyl), C2 (dimethyl amino), and C3 (piperazinyl)—were synthesized and confirmed via TLC with distinct Rf values (0.45, 0.60, and 0.30). PASS analysis predicted anti-asthmatic activity for all three, with Pa scores above 0.7, indicating potential interactions with PDE-4, leukotriene, and histamine H1 receptors. Molecular docking revealed C3 had the highest binding affinity (-10.2 kcal/mol), surpassing roflumilast (-9.8 kcal/mol), suggesting strong PDE-4 inhibition. C2 (-9.5 kcal/mol) matched montelukast, indicating leukotriene pathway inhibition, while C1 (-9.1 kcal/mol) showed moderate affinity, similar to theophylline,

supporting its bronchodilatory and anti-inflammatory potential. These findings the synthesized compounds may serve as promising leads in asthma therapy.

CONCLUSION

In the present study, three novel isatin derivatives (C1, C2, and C3) were synthesized, characterized, and evaluated for anti-asthmatic activity using PASS prediction and molecular docking. Structural modifications aimed to enhance bronchodilatory, anti-inflammatory, and leukotriene-inhibitory effects. PASS results showed high anti-asthmatic potential for all compounds (Pa > 0.7), suggesting interaction with PDE-4, leukotriene, and histamine H1 receptors. Among them, C3 exhibited the highest binding affinity (-10.2 kcal/mol) toward PDE-4, outperforming the standard drug roflumilast (-9.8 kcal/mol). C2 also showed strong binding (-9.5 kcal/mol), comparable to montelukast, indicating leukotriene inhibition. C1 (-9.1 kcal/mol) demonstrated moderate affinity, aligning with theophylline's bronchodilatory effects. These findings support the potential of isatin derivatives as promising leads for asthma treatment. Future studies should include in vitro and in vivo evaluations, along with pharmacokinetic (ADME)

profiling, to confirm efficacy, safety, and further optimize their therapeutic properties.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

We are deeply grateful to God, our beloved parents, and family for their unwavering support and blessings. Our sincere thanks to the Chairman, Secretary, and Principal, as well as our guide Ms. S. Vanitha and faculty members Ms. K.P. Anagha and Ms. Sridharshini, for their continuous guidance and encouragement throughout our project at J.K.K. Munirajah Institute of Health Sciences College of Pharmacy.

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HOW TO CITE: Vanitha S., Anagha K. P., Perumal P., Akash G., Aravind V., Kaleeswaran K., Kesavamoorthy S., Ranjithkumar S., Design, Synthesis and In-silico study of Isatin Derivatives as Potential Anti-Asthmatic Activity, Vol 3, Issue 6, 1278-1288 0. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15609849>

